

CHIZIQSIZ REAKSIYA-DIFFUZIYALI EPIDEMIYA MASALASINI MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISH

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Masalaning qo'yilishi. $Q = \{(t, x) : 0 \leq t \leq T, x \in R_+^1\}$ sohada reaksiya-diffuziya tenglamasi berilgan bo'lsin [1]:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u^\alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + k(x, t)u(1 - u^\beta), \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u|_{t=0} &= u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in R_+^1, \\ u|_{x=0} &= \varphi(t) \geq 0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

(1)-(2) masalada $u_0(x)$ funksiya chekli va quyidagi shartlar bajariladigan funksiyalarni qaraymiz:

$$0 < k(x, t) \leq k(t) \in C(Q), \quad 0 < \varphi(t) \in C^1(0, \infty)$$

$u(t, x)$ yechimni chiziqsiz ajratish usulidan foydalanib, quyidagi shaklda qidiramiz:

$$u(t, x) = \varphi(t)w(\tau(t), x) \quad (3)$$

$\varphi(t)$ quyidagi tenglamaning yechimi:

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = k(t)\varphi(1 - \varphi^\beta), \quad \varphi(t) = \left(1 + e^{-\beta \int_0^t k(y)dy} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (4)$$

Darhaqiqat, (4) va (3) ni hisobga olgan holda (1) ga invariant tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(w^\alpha \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + \varphi_1(t)w(1 - w^\beta),$$

bu yerda $\tau(t)$ yangi noma'lum funksiya va $w(\tau(t), x)$ aniqlanishi kerak bo'lgan funksiya.

(3) ni (1) ga olib borib qo‘ysak, unda quyidagi tenglamaga kelamiz va bundan $\tau(t)$ ni tanlaymiz:

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} w + \varphi(t) \frac{\partial w}{\partial \tau} \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \varphi^{(\alpha+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(w^\alpha \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + k(t) \varphi(t) w (1 - \varphi^\beta w^\beta),$$

$$k(t) \varphi (1 - \varphi^\beta) w + \varphi(t) \frac{\partial w}{\partial \tau} \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \varphi^{(\alpha+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(w^\alpha \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + k(t) \varphi(t) w (1 - \varphi^\beta w^\beta),$$

$\tau(t)$ ni $\frac{d\tau}{dt} \varphi^{-\alpha} = 1$ shart bajariladigan qilib tanlaymiz va tenglamani olamiz:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial \tau} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(w^\alpha \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) + k(t) \varphi^{\beta-\alpha} w (1 - w^\beta), \tag{5}$$

bu yerda $\frac{d\tau}{dt} = \varphi^\alpha$, $\varphi_1(t) = k(t) \varphi^{\beta-\alpha}$ va $\varphi(t)$ funksiya (4) da keltirilgan.

Shubhasiz, (4) ga binoan, agar $\int_0^t k(y) dy$ mavjud bo‘lsa, u holda $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \varphi(t) = 1$. Agar

$\beta \neq \alpha$ bo‘lsa, biz t yetarlicha katta deb $\varphi_1(t) \sim k(t)$ taxmin qilishimiz mumkin. Bundan yana (1) ko‘rinishdagi tenglamani olamiz. Shu sababli $\varphi(t)$ funksiyaning invariant deb ataymiz, bu yerda $u(t, x) = \varphi(t) w(\tau(t), x)$ (1) tenglamaning yechimi, $w(\tau(t), x)$ esa (5) tenglamaning yechimi va (5) tenglama (1) tenglamaning invariantidir.

1-teorema. Faraz qilaylik, $Q = \{(t, x) : t > 0, x \in R_+^1\}$ sohada

$0 \leq u_0(x) \leq 1, x \in R, \xi = \frac{|x|}{(T + \tau(t))^{\frac{1}{2+\alpha}}}$ o‘rinli bo‘lsin. U holda manfiy bo‘lmagan

umumlashgan $u(t, x)$ yechim aniqlangan va yechim uchun quyidagi munosabat o‘rinli bo‘ladi.

$$\varphi(t) (T + \tau(t))^{-\frac{1}{2+\alpha}} \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \leq u(t, x) \leq e^{\int_0^t k(y) \varphi^{\beta-\alpha}(y) dy} (T + \tau(t))^{-\frac{1}{2+\alpha}} \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$$

$$\text{bu yerda } \varphi(t) = \left(1 + e^{-\beta \int_0^t k(y) dy} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta}}, (a)_+ = \max(0, a).$$

Teoremani isboti sifatida (1) masala uchun yechimlarni taqqoslash teoremasi bo‘yicha [2] yuqori bahoni va chiziqsiz ajratish usulini [1-2] qo‘llash orqali quyidan bahoni olamiz. Bundan yechimlarni solishtirish teoremasini [2] qo‘llash natijasida umumiy yechim uchun ushbu tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$u(t, x) = \varphi(t)(T + \tau(t))^{-\frac{1}{2+\alpha}} \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{\frac{1}{\alpha}},$$

$$\text{Bu yerda } \tau(t) = \int_0^t e^{\int_0^y k(y) dy} dz \text{ va } T > 0.$$

Olingan yechim orqali chiziqsiz reaksiya-diffuziyali epidemiya masalasi uchun ayirmali sxema quramiz va sonli tahlilini amalga oshiramiz.

$Q = \{(t, x) : 0 \leq t \leq T, x \in R_+^1\}$ sohada quyidagi Koshi masalani uchun ayirmali sxema ko'rib chiqaylik:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u^\alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + k(x, t)u(1 - u^\beta), \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{cases} u|_{t=0} = u_0(x) \geq 0, & x \in R_+^1, \\ u|_{x=x_0} = \varphi(t), & t \in [0, T], \\ u|_{x=x_n} = \varphi_1(t) = 0, & t \in [0, T] \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

bu yerda, $0 < k(x, t) \leq k(t) \in C(Q)$, $0 < \varphi(t) \in C^1(0, \infty)$.

$$\varphi(t) = \left(1 + e^{-\beta \int_0^t k(y) dy} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta}}, \quad u_0(x, t) = \varphi(t) \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}, \quad \xi = \frac{x}{(\tau(t))^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad \tau(t) = \int_0^t \varphi^\alpha(y) dy.$$

U holda boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$u(0, x) = \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(c - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}, \quad u(t, 0) = \left(1 + e^{-\beta \int_0^t k(y) dy} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\beta}}, \quad u(t, l) = 0, \quad l = 2\sqrt{\frac{c}{\alpha} \tau(t)}.$$

(6), (7) masalaning sonli yechimi uchun $x \in R_+^1$ da x uchun h qadam bilan ϖ_h teng o'lchovli

$$\varpi_h = \{x_i = d + ih, h > 0, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n, d + hn = b\}$$

va vaqt uchun

$$\varpi_{h_1} = \{t_j = jh_1, h_1 > 0, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m, h_1 m = T\}$$

bo'lgan to'r quramiz.

(9), (10) masala uchun balans usulini qo'llagan holda quyidagi oshkormas ayirmali sxema bilan almashtiramiz va $O(h^2 + h_1)$ hatolikka ega ayirmali masalani hosil qilamiz.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{u_{ij+1} - u_{ij}}{h_1} = \frac{1}{h^2} [a(u_{i+1j+1})(u_{i+1j+1} - u_{ij+1}) - a(u_{ij+1})(u_{ij+1} - u_{i-1j+1})] + \\ \quad + ku_{ij+1}(1 - b(u_{ij+1})), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1, \\ u_{i0} = u_0(x_i), \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n, \\ u_{0j} = \varphi(t_j), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m, \\ u_{nj} = \varphi_1(t_j), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

bu yerda $a(u_{ij}) = \frac{u_{ij}^\alpha + u_{i-1j}^\alpha}{2}$ yoki $a(u_{ij}) = \left(\frac{u_{ij} + u_{i-1j}}{2}\right)^\alpha$,

$b(u_{ij+1}) = (u_{ij})^\beta$ formulalar bilan hisoblanadi.

(8) algebraik tenglamalar sistemasi u_{ij+1} ga nisbatan chiziqsiz.

Chiziqsiz tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun har xil iteratsiya usullaridan foydalanamiz va quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} - u_{ij}^{(s+1)}}{h_1} = \frac{1}{h^2} [a(u_{i+1j+1}^{(s)})(u_{i+1j+1}^{(s+1)} - u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)}) - a(u_{ij+1}^{(s)})(u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} - u_{i-1j+1}^{(s+1)})] + \\ + ku_{ij+1}^{(s)}(1 - b(u_{ij+1}^{(s)})), \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1; \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m-1, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

bunda $s = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

- 1) $b(u_{ij+1}) = (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^\beta$ - Pika usuli,
- 2) $b(u_{ij+1}) = u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)}(u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^{\beta-1}$ - maxsus usul,
- 3) $b(u_{ij+1}) = (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^\beta + \beta(u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^{\beta-1}(u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} - u_{ij+1}^{(s)})$ - Nyuton usuli.

Yuqorida berilgan usullardan birini qo'llash orqali chiziqsizlikni yo'qotish [3-4] mumkin va har bir usul uchun (10) belgilashlarni kiritamiz

1) Pika usuli uchun: $A_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{ij+1}^{(s)}), \quad B_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{i+1j+1}^{(s)}), \quad C_i = A_i + B_i + 1,$
 $F_i = u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} + h_1 \cdot k \cdot u_{ij+1}^{(s)} \cdot (1 - (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^\beta), \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, \dots, n-1.$

2) Maxsus usul uchun: $A_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{ij+1}^{(s)}), \quad B_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{i+1j+1}^{(s)}),$
 $C_i = A_i + B_i + 1 + h_1 \cdot k \cdot (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^\beta, \quad F_i = u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} + h_1 \cdot k \cdot u_{ij+1}^{(s)}, \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, \dots, n-1.$

3) Nyuton usuli uchun:

$$A_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{ij+1}^{(s)}), \quad B_i = \frac{h_1}{h^2} \cdot a(u_{i+1,j+1}^{(s)}), \quad C_i = A_i + B_i + 1 + h_1 \cdot k \cdot \beta \cdot (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^\beta,$$

$$F_i = u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} + h_1 \cdot k \cdot u_{ij+1}^{(s)} + h_1 \cdot k \cdot (\beta - 1) \cdot (u_{ij+1}^{(s)})^{\beta+1}, \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Ayirmali tenglamani quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozib olish mumkin:

$$A_i \cdot u_{i-1,j+1}^{(s+1)} - C_i \cdot u_{ij+1}^{(s+1)} + B_i \cdot u_{i+1,j+1}^{(s+1)} = -F_i, \quad s = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \quad i = 1, \dots, n - 1, \quad (11)$$

(11) tenglamalar sistemasini yechish uchun haydash (progonka) usulidan foydalaniladi va hamma sonli hisoblashlarda $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$ deb qaraladi.

Qaralayotgan chiziqsiz reaksiya-diffuziyali epidemiya masalasini matematik modellashtirish uchun Visual Studio C# 2013 muhitida hamda MathCad 2001 packeti orqali dastur yaratildi va parametrlarning mos qiymatlarida quyidagi natijalar 1-2 rasmlarda berilgan:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u^\alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + ku(1 - u^\beta)$$

$$u|_{t=0} = u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in R,$$

$$\begin{cases} u|_{x=0} = \varphi(t), \\ u|_{x=b} = \varphi_1(t) = 0, \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq t \leq T$$

$$u_0(x) = 2^{-\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{1/\alpha}; \quad \varphi(t) = (1 + e^{-k\beta t})^{-\frac{1}{\beta}}$$

$$u(t, x) = \varphi(t) \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{1/\alpha}; \quad \xi = \frac{x}{(\tau(t))^{1/2}}; \quad \tau(t) = \int_0^t (\varphi(y))^\alpha dy$$

alfa	7	a	-2
beta	5	b	2
k	10	N	100
T	100	M	100

0,826368533825...	2,926193449271...
0,854751399907...	0,632431664893...
0,874556376218...	2,216360163459...
0,889333533081...	0,773831162978...
0,900853617550...	2,300064488520...
0,910120794580...	0,898958482475...
0,9177549736688	1,046044416839...
0,924162885074...	0,909774636312...
0,929623987498...	1,416487394779...
0,934337393512...	0,936578248310...
0,938449206996...	1,175061283155...
0,942069283975...	0,944843059970...
0,945281945637...	0,943746283154...
0,948153067200...	1,061181425107

Sonli natija

1-

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u^\alpha \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + ku(1 - u^\beta)$$

$$u|_{t=0} = u_0(x) \geq 0, \quad x \in R,$$

$$\begin{cases} u|_{x=0} = \varphi(t), \\ u|_{x=b} = \varphi_1(t) = 0, \end{cases} \quad 0 \leq t \leq T$$

$$u_0(x) = 2^{-\frac{1}{\beta}} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{1/\alpha}; \quad \varphi(t) = (1 + e^{-k\beta t})^{-\frac{1}{\beta}}$$

$$u(t, x) = \varphi(t) \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{4} \xi^2 \right)_+^{1/\alpha}; \quad \xi = \frac{x}{(\tau(t))^{1/2}}; \quad \tau(t) = \int_0^t (\varphi(y))^\alpha dy$$

alfa	3	a	-2
beta	5	b	2
k	10	N	100
T	100	M	100

rasm.

0	0
0	0
0	0
0.522757958574...	0
0.693361274350...	0.114532260094...
0.768880959828...	0.837309679535...
0.813551211047...	0.540253703034...
0.843432665301...	0.949660818106...
0.864930585062...	0.720388831591...
0.881177197910...	1.157115528176...
0.893903535096...	0.867520347945...
0.904149740081...	1.026834870606...
0.912580527077...	0.901444711259...
0.919641392127...	1.021909335641...
0.927610101510...	0.807410656678...

Sonli natija

$\alpha = 7, \beta = 5, k = 10$, hol uchun masalaning yechimi.

2-rasm. $\alpha = 3, \beta = 5, k = 10$, hol uchun masalaning yechimi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR RO‘YXATI: (REFERENCES)

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